

Edge chipping at small scales and strengths of diced components

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The morphology of cracks and chips formed by sharp particle contacts adjacent to edges of brittle materials is investigated, along with the resulting component strengths. Controlled indentations are used as model sharp contacts and the edge-chipping behavior of indentation flaws is studied using variations in contact load and edge proximity. The load and length scales studied are newtons and micrometers, respectively. The materials focus is on the behavior of single crystal Si and polycrystalline $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$. The variation of indentation crack lengths parallel to edges is studied along with the critical condition for chip initiation from such cracks. The ensuing variation of chip size as a function of contact load and edge proximity is examined. The small-scale chip initiation and size responses are in agreement with large-scale chip measurements. The small-scale chip initiation and size measurements are combined with indentation-strength measurements to form upper and lower bound strength predictions as a function of edge-chip scallop size. Comparison with commercially-diced and inspected Si components validates the approach.

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1. Introduction

A recent overview highlighted the pervasive nature of edge chipping by sharp particle contacts [Lawn, 2021]. Examples were given describing the detriments and applications of chipping in anthropological, artistic, biomedical, geological, and industrial contexts. Quantitative attention in the overview was focused on the conditions for chipping in terms of proximity of a contacting particle to a component edge and load on the particle. The measurements considered were primarily macroscopic, with length scales of order millimeters (mm) and load scales of order kilonewtons (kN). The report here will extend the overview and present experimental measurements, also in an industrial context, of edge chipping related to sawing of components to size. Specifically, such sawing is known as “dicing” in the manufacture of semiconductor and magnetic storage devices, and edge damage during or subsequent to dicing is the focus here. Large wafers are used as substrates during the fabrication of such devices and the wafers are sawn or diced into many rectangular dies at fabrication completion, each die containing a single semiconducting or magnetic device. Avoidance of defects associated with edge chipping during wafer dicing is thus a critical aspect of maximizing device manufacturing yield [Lei, 2012]. This report will focus on the chipping behavior of the two most important wafer materials in the semiconductor and magnetic storage industries, single crystal silicon (Si) and the polycrystalline ceramic composite $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$. These materials were not considered earlier. In addition, the report here will extend the earlier work in two other ways: (i) the length and load scales for edge chipping will be smaller, micrometers (μm) and newtons (N), respectively; and (ii) the experiments and analyses will include the resulting fracture strengths of chipped components.

The major characteristics of an edge chip are shown in Fig. 1. A sharp particle impinges on a material surface near a component edge and undergoes a load-unload contact cycle with peak load P . The distance of the contact point from the edge is h . If the peak load P is large enough or the contact distance h is small enough, an edge chip is formed by fracture on a curved surface adjacent to the edge. The chip fracture surface extends from the contact, predominantly parallel to the edge, before curving and exiting the material on the contact surface, the edge, and the free surface, predominantly perpendicular to all three. The distance from the fracture exit on the free surface to the component edge is s (cf [Chai and Lawn, 2007a]), taken as the characteristic size of the chip and most often $s > h$. The separation of the fracture exits on the component edge is D [Chai and Lawn, 2007a]. Often, but not always, the chip outline on the free surface is approximately semi-circular such that $D \approx 2s$. If P is too small or h too large, fracture may still occur along a curved surface at the contact but if the cracks formed do not exit the material no chip is generated. The development of edge chips from contact cracks as P and h are varied is a focus of this work, along with the subsequent variations in s .

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of an edge chip (shaded) formed by a sharp contact, load P , distance h from edge (dashed). The chip dimensions perpendicular and parallel to the edge are s and D , respectively.

Three aspects of edge chipping are major concerns in dicing and are illustrated in [Fig. 2](#). The first concern is the removal of chipped material from the die to form very small loose particles of wafer material leading to device defects in subsequent manufacturing processes. An example of an edge chip leading to a free particle is shown in [Fig. 2\(a\)](#), which shows a micrometer-scale chip formed during dicing of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$. The striations of the diced surface are apparent in the upper section of the image, the polished surface of the front face of the wafer is apparent in the lower section of the image, and the grains of the polycrystalline ceramic are apparent on the curved chip surface. The contact that caused the chip was on the diced surface leading to a nearly semi-circular chip outline on the polished surface, similar to that shown in Fig. 1. A second example of an edge chip leading to a free particle is shown in [Fig. 2\(b\)](#), which shows a hundred micrometer-scale chip formed during dicing of Si. In this case, the diced edge is apparent at the top of the image, remnant film deposition features on the back face of the wafer are apparent in the lower section of the image, and ripple markings associated with fracture in single crystal Si are apparent on the curved chip surface. The contact that caused the chip was on the diced surface, not shown, leading to a typical scallop-shaped chip outline on the wafer back face and $D < s$. Edge chip “scallops” and “scalloping” during dicing are extremely common.

Figure 2. Images of edge chips illustrating deleterious effects of dicing. (a) Chip in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$ polished polycrystal. (b) Chip in single crystal Si on die back face. (c) Chip in single crystal Si on die front face with material attached. (d) Chip in single crystal Si on die back face and initiated failure crack.

The second concern arising from edge chipping during dicing is the direct generation of defects in devices fabricated on the wafer front face. An example of an edge chip leading to a device defect is shown in [Fig. 2\(c\)](#), which shows a hundred-micrometer scale chip formed by die handling subsequent to dicing of Si. Here, the diced edge is apparent on the right of the image, active device features on the wafer front face are apparent in the left of the image, and the displaced chip associated with sub-surface fracture in single crystal Si is apparent (the chip is held in place by electrostatic effects). The contact that caused the chip was on the diced surface, leading to a scallop-shaped chip outline on the wafer front face. The third concern arising from edge chipping during dicing is the generation of strength-controlling flaws leading to complete die failure in subsequent die handling and, particularly, packaging. The common packaging geometry of active front face attachment of a die to a polymer substrate places a tensile stress in

the die back face. The stress is a driving force for brittle fracture of Si from back face cracks associated with edge chips. An example of complete die failure caused by crack propagation from an edge chip is shown in Fig. 2(d), which shows a Si die back face similar to that in Fig. 2(b). The crack extending across the die from top to bottom is apparent. The variation of die strength σ with the edge chip parameters P , h , and s is another focus of this work.

This report is divided into a further four sections. In the next section (2), the overall development of an edge chip from a sharp contact flaw is described as P is increased or h is decreased. The experimental variations of crack lengths at contacts influenced by an edge but in the pre-chip state are presented. This section also presents experimental measurements of the threshold conditions for chipping in terms of contact load and edge proximity relations and compares the small-scale results here with the earlier larger-scale observations [Chai and Lawn, 2007a]. The following section (3) presents and compares experimental measurements of the most obvious manifestation of chipping, the variation of characteristic chip size s in terms of (P, h) contact conditions in the post-chip state. In sections 2 and 3, Vickers indentations are used as model sharp contacts to generate controlled edge chips. The next section (4) presents experimental measurements of die strengths controlled by edge-chips, including those generated by dicing flaws and model indentation flaws. The final section (5) summarizes the work here in context and suggests some directions for future work.

2. Sharp contact cracking at edges

2.1. Contact morphology

Model sharp contact flaws are formed by a Vickers diamond pyramid indenter. Such flaws are often used in contact and fracture testing, were used in earlier edge chipping studies [Chai and Lawn, 2007a; Lawn, 2021], and are also used here. An advantage of indentation flaws is that the contact load and location can be controlled, thereby controlling chip formation. Indentation contacts also have the advantage of mimicking the essential aspects of “natural” sharp contact flaws, including the formation of a plastic deformation zone and cracks localized to the contact [Lawn and Cook, 2012; Marshall *et al.*, 2015]. The following qualitative description of edge chip development is based on extensive observations in many materials of controlled indentation deformation and fracture adjacent to component edges. The greatest experimental concern is variation in the indentation distance to an edge, h , although variations in the indentation load, P , also strongly influences behavior. The description is summarized in Fig. 3. The sequence (a), (b), (c), (d) illustrates indentation behavior at fixed P as h is decreased from a very large value for indentations remote from an edge to a very small value for indentations close to an edge.

Figure 3. Schematic plan-view diagram of edge chip development at Vickers indentation contacts. Contact impression shown shaded. (a) Remote from the edge: standard indentation. (b) Near the edge: cracks elongated parallel to edge. (c) Critical distance to edge: cracks elongated and curved to reach edge and form chip. (d) Close to edge: cracks curved and truncated by edge to form small chip.

Figure 3(a) shows a schematic plan view diagram of a “standard” Vickers indentation formed far from a component edge. The indentation contact generates a residual square surface impression, shown shaded, of semi-diagonal a . The diagonal dimension is fixed at peak load, such that the mean contact pressure or hardness is $H = P/2a^2$. Inverting this equation gives the variation of a with P for materials with invariant hardness:

$$a = (1/2H)^{1/2}P^{1/2}. \quad (1)$$

The contact also generates an approximately hemispherical sub-surface plastic deformation zone (not shown) of characteristic dimension $b > a$ [Lawn, 2021] and the ratio b/a is a load-invariant material parameter. During the contact cycle, cracks are initiated in the plastic deformation zone, propagate into the surrounding elastic matrix, and stabilized at lengths in equilibrium with the indentation residual stress field set by b/a . The most important of these cracks for chip formation and strength control are half-penny cracks with semi-circular outlines centered on the plastic deformation zone [Cook and Pharr, 1990; Cook, 2019]. At a standard indentation, two identical, perpendicular, half-penny cracks are formed, aligned parallel to the indenter diagonals and extending into the contacted surface. The surface traces of the half-penny cracks are of length c . The variation of c with P is given by

$$c = BP^{2/3}, \quad (2)$$

where B is the material- and indenter-dependent cracking susceptibility [Cook, 2020a]. B is predominantly dependent inversely on the material toughness T in the indentation environment and weakly dependent on the b/a ratio set by the indenter and material (b/a can be expressed in

terms of E/H , where E is the material's Young's modulus). Hence, for materials with invariant toughness, B is invariant. Combining Eqs. (1) and (2) to eliminate P leads to

$$c/a^{4/3} = (2H)^{2/3}B, \quad (3)$$

which implies that the adjusted crack-length ratio $c/a^{4/3}$ should be load-invariant for standard indentations far from an edge. Extensive measurements over extended load domains on many materials are well described by Eqs. (1), (2), and (3) [Cook, 2020]. Deviations in the ratio $c/a^{4/3}$ should thus be a sensitive measure of edge effects.

Figure 3(b) shows a schematic view of a Vickers indentation close to an edge. The indentation impression and thus perceived hardness are unaffected by the edge, as are the surface traces of the half-penny cracks perpendicular to the edge. However, the surface traces of the half-penny cracks parallel to the edge are elongated and curved towards the edge. In the presence of an edge, the compliance introduced by the free surface beyond the edge significantly perturbs the indentation stress field adjacent to the contact. As a consequence, the driving force for the half-penny crack parallel to the free surface is considerably enhanced relative to the perpendicular crack, which experiences little to no compliance change and is thus relatively unaffected. Figure 4 shows examples of Vickers indentations on various materials with enhanced cracking adjacent to edges. An indentation on soda-lime silicate glass is shown in Fig. 4(a) and the distance h to the edge (top of image) is indicated. The significantly elongated and curved cracks, initially parallel to the edge are apparent, as is the slightly elongated crack perpendicular to and truncated by the edge. The bright areas are reflections from lateral cracks parallel to the indented surface [Cook, 2019; Lawn, 2021]. The shaded areas are diminished reflections from the half-penny cracks initially perpendicular to the indented surface and curving towards the free surface [Chai and Lawn, 2007a] (note the lack of shading and curvature on the perpendicular half-penny cracks). This overall contact morphology is extremely common. At greater a/h ratios, the crack curvature is greater, as shown in Fig. 4(b) by an indentation on a diced Si surface (the striations were formed in dicing). The crack perpendicular to the edge is slightly longer and truncated by the edge as in Fig. 4(a). At smaller a/h ratios, the crack curvature is less, as shown in Fig. 4(c) by an indentation on a polished Si surface. The cracks perpendicular to the edge are both shorter in this case. At very small a/h ratios, no cracks perpendicular to the edge may form, as shown in Fig. 4(d) by an indentation in an Al_2O_3 coating on an Al_2O_3 -TiC substrate. In this case, the indentation is too small (sub-threshold) to initiate cracks when placed remote from an edge. However, near an edge the enhanced driving force arising from the adjacent free surface initiates cracks parallel to the edge.

Figure 4. Images of indentation flaws adjacent to component edges illustrating enhanced cracking parallel to the edge (top in each image): (a) soda-lime silicate glass; (b) diced Si surface; (c) polished Si surface; and (d) diced cross-section of Al_2O_3 film on Al_2O_3 -TiC ceramic composite substrate.

2.2. Crack lengths

Figure 4 makes clear that edge proximity primarily affects contact-induced cracks parallel to an edge. This effect is demonstrated quantitatively in [Fig. 5](#), which shows the variation of crack length c as a function of distance from the edge h for indentation cracks in Al_2O_3 -TiC. The indentation load was $P = 25$ N, resulting in a contact dimension of $a \approx 30$ μm . The open and closed symbols represent measurements of individual crack lengths, perpendicular and parallel to the edge, respectively. Remote from the edge, $h \approx 10a$, both sets of crack are similar, $c \approx 50$ μm , indicated by the solid horizontal line. As h was decreased, the cracks perpendicular to the edge did not vary appreciably in length. However, the cracks parallel to the edge increased significantly in length as h was decreased until the critical distance for chipping was reached, $h \approx 3a$, and the cracks exited the material in the configuration shown in the schematic diagram

of Fig. 3(c). At indentation locations closer to the edge than this, chips formed, indicated by the cross-hatched region. Figure 6 shows measurements as a function of indentation load of crack lengths parallel to an edge in soda-lime silicate glass. At each load indicated, symbols represent individual crack lengths and chipping occurred at all distances less than the smallest indicated. The behavior is similar to that of Fig. 5. Remote from the edge, cracks lengths are small and tend to an invariant length. Near the edge, the crack lengths increase significantly. At a critical distance, decreasing with decreasing load, chipping and material removal occurred.

Figure 5. Crack length as a function of distance to an edge for indentation cracks in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$. The cracks parallel to an edge increase in length significantly as the edge is approached before chipping occurs. Cracks perpendicular to the edge are unaffected.

Figure 6. Lengths of cracks parallel to an edge for indentations in soda-lime silicate glass at the indentation loads indicated. Crack lengths increase with increasing load and edge proximity.

Materials comparisons of edge effects on indentation crack lengths, *e.g.*, between Figs. 5 and 6, and assessment of indentation load effects, *e.g.*, of the various indentation load responses in Fig. 6, is accomplished using the adjusted crack length. Figure 7(a) replots the crack length c data of Fig. 6 as an adjusted crack length ordinate $c/a^{4/3}$, following Eq. (6) and using the measured a values for each load. For simplicity, the abscissa in Fig. 7(a) also follows Eq. (6) to generate an adjusted edge distance $h/a^{4/3}$. As expected, the adjusted crack length data lie on a load-independent response, indicated as a guide to the eye by the solid line. At large adjusted distances to the edge, the adjusted crack lengths tend to an invariant value. At small adjusted distances to the edge, $h/a^{4/3} \approx 1 \mu\text{m}^{-1/3}$, the adjusted crack lengths increase significantly, before chipping occurs at very small adjusted distances (some small, sub-threshold, indentations have no cracks). Figures 7(b) and 7(c) show similar plots of adjusted edge cracking parameters for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$ and Si, respectively. The behavior is qualitatively similar to that of Fig. 7(a): invariant adjusted crack lengths far from an edge and significant increases in crack length near an edge prior to the onset of chipping. Material dependencies are revealed in quantitative comparisons of invariant adjusted crack lengths remote from an edge and in adjusted distances to an edge at which crack lengths increase.

Figure 7. Plots of adjusted indentation crack length as a function of adjusted distance to an edge for three materials. (a) Soda-lime silicate glass. (b) $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$. (c) Si. In all three materials, use of adjusted parameters removes indentation load dependence and illustrates the increase in crack length adjacent to edges.

2.3. Chipping threshold

In Fig. 6, the edge distances at which crack lengths increase significantly exhibit some dispersion, about a factor of 0.3 in relative adjusted edge distance coordinates $h/a^{4/3}$, implying sensitivity of the crack driving force to the details of contact and edge geometry. Similar dispersion is also observed in the critical condition for chipping at small edge distances, implying a similar sensitivity of the chip initiation conditions to contact and edge geometry. An example of dispersion in the critical condition for chipping is shown in Fig. 8, which is a semi-logarithmic plot of the probability of chip formation in Si as a function of adjusted edge distance for four indentation loads. As in Fig. 7, the use of the adjusted edge distance removes the load dependence. Consistent with Fig. 7(c), chipping was observed at adjusted distances of approximately 2 (< 2.5 , see Fig 7(c)) with dispersion about a relative factor of 0.5. The implication is that chip initiation is a probabilistic phenomenon if the macroscopic parameter of $h/a^{4/3}$ is the sole controlled variable.

Figure 8. Plot of chip probability as a function of adjusted edge distance for several indentation loads in Si. Remote from the edge, the probability of indentation-induced chipping is zero. Close to the edge the probability increases to certainty over a range of adjusted edge distances. Approximately ten indentations/point.

The data of Fig. 8 were obtained with a technique of performing a series of indentations in the configurations of Figs. 3(b), 3(c), and 3(d), and determining probabilities within the tested (P, h) domain. A second technique is to perform a series of static indentations in configuration 3(b) and halt investigation when configuration 3(c) is encountered. This approach provides an

upper bound to the (P, h) conditions defining the domain of configuration 3(c); uncertainty in h is generated as P is controlled. Yet a third technique is to perform a single dynamic indentation and observe the indentation *in situ* as P is increased and halt the experiment when configuration 3(c) is encountered. This approach provides a lower bound to the (P, h) conditions defining the domain of configuration 3(c); uncertainty in P is generated as h is controlled. This latter technique was that implemented in a previous macro-scale study [Chai and Lawn, 2007a], although uncertainties were not given.

Figure 9 shows estimations of the initiation conditions for indentation edge chip formation in (P, h) coordinates for several materials, configuration 3(c), using the three techniques above. The open symbols represent observations from the present micro-scale study, with bars representing the estimated uncertainties. The solid symbols represent observations from a macro-scale study [Chai and Lawn, 2007a] digitized from published results, recognizing these as lower bounds. The solid line is the published $P \sim h^{3/2}$ empirical fit to the macro scale glass data.

Figure 9. Plot of indentation edge chip initiation conditions expressed in terms of contact load P and edge distance h . Macro-scale and micro-scale observations are in agreement.

The data from tests at the micro-scale (about 100 μm edge distance) and macro-scale (about 1000 μm edge distance) are in agreement both qualitatively and quantitatively. Tougher materials (alumina, zirconia) exhibit greater chip initiation loads (relative to glass) at the macro-scale and

the micro-scale ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$ exhibits greater initiation loads than glass). Over a factor of 10^2 in edge distance, and therefore 10^3 in load, the $P \sim h^{3/2}$ trend is observed. Extrapolation of the glass behavior from the macro scale to the micro scale underestimates the critical edge distance by a relative factor of about 0.3. As the extrapolation does not take in to account the lower bound nature of the the macro-scale data, the underestimation is consistent with the probabilistic data of Fig. 8.

3. Edge chip size variation

Figures 5-7 of section 2.2. considered variations in the chip-free configuration, Fig. 3(b). Figures 8 and 9 of section 2.3. considered variations in the chip initiation configuration, Fig. 3(c). In this section, variations in the well-developed chip configuration, Fig. 3(d), are considered. An example of chip size variation for indentation flaws in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$ is shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10. Images of edge chips in $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiC}$ generated by indentations on the contact face perpendicular to the chip. Edge distances of $h = 20 \mu\text{m}$ to $3 \mu\text{m}$ were used to form the chips from largest to smallest, (a)-(d).

A particular focus of edge chip characterization is the variation in chip size s on the non-contacted, free surface, Fig. 1, as a function of contact load P and edge proximity h . In contrast to the two previous sections, in which indentation crack lengths were observed to become longer and chipping prevalence was observed to increase as edge proximity h decreased, chip size s will be seen to decrease as h decreases. An example of this behavior is shown in Fig. 10, in which the flaws were created from largest to smallest, (a)-(d), using indentation loads from $P = 3$ N to 0.25 N with associated impression dimensions of approximately $a = 4$ μm to 2 μm . Edge distances were $h = 20$ μm to 3 μm . The scallop size s decreased from approximately 100 μm to 10 μm —the potency of the free edge to generate chips at sharp contacts is clear as $s > h$ and a . The commonly observed variation in chip morphology with size is also noticeable in Fig. 10: larger chips, (a) and (b), are oblate ($D > s$, Fig. 1), moderate chips, (c), are near semi-circular ($D \approx s$), and small chips, (d), are slightly prolate ($D < s$). The tilt of the specimen showing the smallest chip in Fig. 10(d) enables the intact half of the contact impression to be observed on the indented face. In this case, the impression size and chip size are comparable to the scale of the microstructure. The similarity between the small-scale artificial chip of Fig. 10(d) and the dicing related natural chip of Fig. 2(a) is clear.

Figure 11 shows logarithmic plots of the variations in chip size s with edge distance h for small scale chipping of (a) two Al_2O_3 -TiC systems and (b) Si. Also shown in Fig. 11 (small open symbols) are the responses observed for large scale chipping of zirconia, alumina, porcelain, and glass digitized from the published results of an earlier study [Chai and Lawn, 2007a], along with a characteristic linear response for large chips, $s = 5h$ (solid line). For the Al_2O_3 -TiC and Si measurements presented here, a range of indentation loads P was used, leading to a range of contact dimensions a . In the case of the Al_2O_3 -TiC systems, all indentation loads used were sub-threshold. That is, remote from an edge no indentation generated an indentation half-penny crack. In the case of Si, all indentation loads used were post-threshold. That is, remote from an edge all indentations generated indentation half-penny cracks. The impression dimensions a for the Al_2O_3 -TiC systems varied from 2 μm to 14 μm , those for Si varied from 4 μm to 16 μm . The edge distances h for the Al_2O_3 -TiC systems varied from 3 μm to 50 μm , those for Si varied from 2 μm to 80 μm . For each value of h , five to eight indentations were made and the symbols with bars in Fig. 11 represent the means and standard deviations of the experimentally observed s dimensions. For both Al_2O_3 -TiC and Si, only a few indentations at the larger h values exhibited chipping and measurements in Si for these cases are represented as isolated symbols. Different symbols in Fig. 11 represent different P values. Optical microscopy was used for all measurements.

Figure 11. Plots of chip dimensions as a function of edge distances for (a) Al₂O₃-TiC and (b) Si. Different symbols represent different indentation loads. Small symbols and solid line represent results from a prior large-scale study [Chai and Lawn, 2007a].

The solid symbols in Fig. 11(a) represent the Al₂O₃-TiC system shown in the images of Figs. 2(a) and 10. The chipping data for this material are slightly overestimated by a linear response extrapolated from larger scale data associated with earlier work [Chai and Lawn, 2007a]. The large open symbols in Fig. 11(a) represent the Al₂O₃ film-Al₂O₃-TiC substrate system shown in the image of Fig. 4(d). The data for this material exhibit slightly larger chip dimensions for a given edge distance than the bare Al₂O₃-TiC system. Observations of chipping in the film on substrate system suggest a weak tendency to interfacial fracture that may explain the slightly greater chip dimensions. The data for the Al₂O₃ film on Al₂O₃-TiC system are well described by the extrapolated linear response. The solid symbols in Fig. 11(b) represent the Si system shown in the image of Fig. 2(b). In this case, the chipping data at the largest h values for the material are well described by the extrapolated linear response, but the smaller h value data are clearly underestimated. In more detail, the Si data deviate systematically from the extrapolated linear response for edge distances less than the largest distance to give rise to chipping at a given indentation load. Specifically, the Si responses at each load exhibit greater chip sizes and a weaker dependence of chip size on edge distance, approximately $s \sim h^{1/2}$.

Two major points may be drawn from Fig. 11. The first point, supporting the conclusion reached in the earlier work [Chai and Lawn, 2007a], is that chip size s as a function of edge distance h is predominantly material invariant. The results here add three more material responses in support of this conclusion and extend the domain of applicability by a factor of 100 to smaller scales. The second point builds on the discussion above regarding the determination by different test methods of different bounds on chipping parameters. The macro-scale tests provided lower bounds on the chip sizes s at each edge distance h , as the reported $s(h)$ responses (small, open symbols) reflected the minimum contact load chip initiation condition, Fig. 3(c). The micro-scale tests provide the lower bounds and greater values of s at each h value, as loading continues beyond the minimum initiation condition to greater loads if the minimum condition does not generate a chip. As a consequence of the overload, longer transverse cracks, Figs. 3(b) and 7, are generated prior to chipping and thus larger chips are eventually generated from these larger pre-cursors. As a consequence, materials that generate many chip initiation features during indentation contact will tend to the solid line $s(h)$ lower bound, such as Al₂O₃-TiC in Fig. 11(a). Materials that generate chip initiation features in a gradual, probabilistic manner during contact will exhibit a range of $s(h)$ responses greater than the lower bound, such as Si in Fig. 11(b). Hence the first point above should probably be modified to state that chipping behavior is material invariant for the lower bound contact conditions pertaining to chip initiation.

Another way of looking at this second point regarding bounds on chipping is to replot the Si data of Fig. 11(b) as chip aspect ratio, s/h , as a function of the adjusted impression size, a/h , as shown in Fig. 12. At a given edge distance, as the impression size, and thus peak contact load,

increases, the chip aspect ratio increases from the minimum value of 5 to almost 20. In physical terms, small contacts far from the edge generate “stubby” chips and large contacts close to the edge generate “slender,” shard-like chips. The minimum aspect ratio stubby chips reflect a material invariant lower bound on chip initiation. That is, the probability of chip initiation is increased if the load and thus impression dimension are increased beyond the threshold at a given edge distance, or if the edge distance is decreased at the threshold load. In either case, the chip aspect ratio becomes more slender.

Figure 12. Plot of chip aspect ratio as a function of adjusted impression size for Si. Different symbols represent different indentation loads and are displaced for clarity. An aspect ratio of 5 observed for chips generated by relatively small impressions reflects a material invariant lower bound on edge chipping.

4. Edge chip strength variation

In addition to damaging active devices and creating loose particles of material, Figs. 2(a)-(c), edge chips formed during or subsequent to dicing decrease the failure load of a component by generating strength-controlling flaws, Fig. 2(d). The most visible feature of such flaws is the scallop shaped chip of material removed from the component edge and the connection between a visible scallop and a crack propagating across a component is often clear. Hence, assessments of “edge quality” usually quantify the number and size of scallops visible on diced edges, with the

expectation that such parameters will correlate not just with device damage and particle creation, but with component strength.

There are two major reasons why such a scallop size-component strength correlation might not be straightforward. First, the predominant plane of the scallop crack is parallel to the free surface. The cracks that control component strength are perpendicular to the free surface, however, as is the tensile stress applied to the component subsequent to scallop formation (often by bending). Although the size of a scallop is related to the size of a strength controlling crack by the contact load, edge proximity has a much greater effect on scallop size than on the lengths of cracks perpendicular to the edge, c_s , Fig. 3(c). Plan view inspection of scallop dimensions does not provide information regarding the aspect ratio of the scallop or the likely contact load or dimensions. Estimating the perpendicular crack length is thus difficult. The second reason for uncertainty in strength estimation from scallop size measurements is that an edge contact removes a substantial, but unknown fraction, of the plastic deformation zone beneath a contact, along with the scallop shaped particle of material. Plastic deformation zones at contacts generate significant residual stress fields and thus driving forces for crack propagation, including cracks perpendicular to edges. The driving force for crack propagation is thus reduced in a variable manner by scallop formation.

Hence, visual inspections can certainly enable assessments of edge “roughness” and provide clear predictions for the direct effects of chipping, such as generation of device defects and free particles. However, as edge chipping is an indirect measure of strength-limiting flaws, edge inspections can only provide bounds on the strengths of components limited by near edge contacts. The rest of this section builds on the previous two sections to provide such bounds and interpret the results of a study of edge chipping and strength in diced Si components.

4.1. Strength measurements

Figure 13 shows logarithmic plots of the strength σ of Si dies containing controlled indentation flaws. The dies were approximately 15 mm \times 8 mm \times 0.7 mm and were strength tested in four-point bending perpendicular to the long axis of the die. Flaws were introduced on the 15 mm \times 0.7 mm die face at specified distances h from the prospective tensile die edge. The same set of indentation loads P used in Figs. 11 and 12 were used to introduce the flaws. The strengths of dies containing no such flaws and considered by optical inspection to exhibit no significant edge scallop (active 15 mm \times 8 mm die faces, defects $< 1 \mu\text{m}$) are shown as the gray bands, (529 \pm 77) MPa, and this strength is referred to as the intrinsic strength of the dies. The strengths of dies containing introduced edge flaws were all less than this value. At least eight dies for each (P, h) combination were indented, examined for the formation of a scallop, and strength tested.

Figure 13. Logarithmic plots of strength σ for Si dies containing indentation flaws located distance h from die edges. Indentation loads indicated. Grey bars indicate indentation-free intrinsic strengths. (a) Closed symbol data for indentation flaws with edge scallops. (b) Open symbol data for indentation flaws with no scallop.

The filled symbols in [Fig. 13\(a\)](#) represent the strengths of dies containing indentation flaws that exhibited an edge chip in the form of a removed scallop of material, Figs. 2(b), 3(c), 3(d), 10. The symbols with bars represent the means and standard deviations of at least five strength measurements at the (P, h) combinations indicated. Other symbols represent individual strength measurements. As in Figs. 11 and 12, smaller indentation loads P , and thus smaller contact impressions a , enabled smaller h values to be examined. Also as in Figs. 11 and 12, at larger

edge distances the probability of scallop formation decreased, indicated by the increasing proportion of individual symbols at large h values for a given P value. The solid lines are guides to the eye and connect the median strengths at each h value for a specified value of P . There is a clear decrease in strength with increasing edge distance, both within a fixed P set and between P values. The dashed lines are upper and lower bounds to the data. The strength lower bound is of the form $\sigma \sim h^{-0.5}$ and corresponds to the material-invariant lower bound for scallop initiation indicated in Fig. 11. The strength upper bound is of the form $\sigma \sim h^{-0.20}$ and corresponds to the deviations to larger scallop sizes exhibited by Si from the material-invariant bound of Fig. 11. The bounds are considered in greater detail in the following sub-section.

The open symbols in Fig. 13(b) represent the strengths of dies containing indentation flaws that exhibited no scallop, Figs. 3(b) and 4. The symbols with bars represent the means and standard deviations of at least five strength measurements at the (P, h) combinations indicated. Other symbols represent individual strength measurements. As in Fig. 6, smaller indentation loads P , and thus smaller contact impressions a , enabled smaller h values to be examined. As in Fig. 8, at smaller edge distances the probability of scallop formation increased, indicated by the increasing proportion of individual symbols at small h values for a given P value. The solid and dashed lines are reproduced from Fig. 13(a) and are the guides to the eye and bounds for the scallop strength data, respectively. As in Fig. 13(a), the scallop-free strength data exhibit a clear decrease in strength with increasing edge distance, both within a fixed P set and between P values. The scallop-free strength data are only marginally greater than the scallop median strength trends for selected indentation loads and for all loads are well within the upper and lower bounds determined for the scallop strength data. The similarity in strengths supports the expectation above that information regarding scallop size alone, or, as here, even scallop presence or absence, may be an insufficient indicator of strength. The following sub-section illustrates how the data of Fig.13, when combined with those from Figs. 9 and 11, can provide practical strength prediction bounds for direct comparison with industrially-based measurements.

4.2. Strength analysis and prediction

In industrial microelectronics production, Si devices are always inspected visually after dicing to assess edge quality, usually to estimate electrical yield loss due to edge chip or scallop formation and disruption of the active device, Fig. 2(a). The parameters most often reported are the active face scallop density expressed as number of scallops/edge length, mean scallop size, and maximum observed scallop size. The devices are sometimes inspected visually on the (diced) side face, and rarely, if ever, inspected mechanically by strength testing. Hence, yield loss and reliability truncation due to handling and packaging stresses large relative to die strength must be

estimated from visual inspection data. Such estimates require dedicated experiments in which the same sets of dies undergo both the customary visual inspection and strength testing.

Here, three different form factors of fully fabricated commercial dies were sawn to size, all approximately $15 \text{ mm} \times 8 \text{ mm}$, in 38 different dicing runs. After the completed production sequences, the dies were inspected visually using standard protocols and the scallop values reported for each dicing run as the average scallop size and the maximum observed scallop size. Approximately 10 dies were sampled randomly from each run after visual inspection and subsequently strength tested in bending. In a separate control experiment, approximately 80 dies were sampled randomly from the dicing runs and indented so as to generate an edge scallop and the scallop size measured. The strengths of these dies were then also tested in bending.

Figure 14 is a logarithmic plot of the strength σ of the Si dies containing both artificial and dicing scallops as a function of scallop size s . Note that h , P , and a are not known for these dies. The shaded bar represents the intrinsic strength of pristine dies, repeated from Fig. 13. The open symbols with bars represent measurements of the dies containing dicing scallops. Different open symbols represent different die form factors; there was no significant distinction. An open symbol position indicates the mean die strength and the mean scallop size for a dicing run. The vertical bars indicate the standard deviations of the strength measurements. The horizontal bars indicate the maximum scallop dimension observed in a dicing run. The solid symbols represent measurements of individual dies containing the artificial indentation scallops. The strength data for the dicing and artificial scallops overlap considerably and exhibit a clear decrease in strength with increasing scallop size. The dashed lines in Fig. 14 are lower- and upper-bound predictions of the strength, based on the separate strength results of Fig. 13 and determined as follows.

The lower-bound strength prediction is based on the material-invariant scallop (chip) initiation load response of Fig. 9, which shows that the contact load for scallop initiation varies with edge distance as

$$P \sim h^{3/2}. \quad (3)$$

Comparison with Eq. (2) implies that the crack perpendicular to the edge at scallop initiation, Fig. 3(c), notated here as c_s , should thus vary linearly with edge distance,

$$c_s \sim h. \quad (4)$$

This crack controls component strength, but is not involved in scallop formation and only observed in section view, Figs. 3 and 4, but not plan view, Fig. 2. Approximating the strength variation with crack length to be described by the Griffith equation [Lawn, 1993], gives

$$\sigma \sim c_s^{-1/2}, \quad (5)$$

and thus for strength-controlling cracks formed at scallop initiation, using Eq. (3),

$$\sigma \sim h^{-1/2}. \quad (6)$$

The final step is to replace the unknown edge distance with the measured scallop size using the material invariant lower bound response of Fig. 11,

$$s \sim h. \tag{7}$$

Hence, from Eqs. (6) and (7), the variation of strength with scallop size is

$$\sigma \sim s^{-1/2}. \tag{8}$$

Equation (8) is lower bound to the strength as Fig. 11(b) shows that similar sized scallops may be generated over a range of contact loads, if the smaller loads are further from the edge. A smaller load gives rise to a smaller crack and therefore a greater strength. As edge distance, contact load, and strength-controlling crack size are all unknown, Eq. (8) is thus a lower bound variation.

Figure 14. Plot of Si die strength as a function of edge chip scallop size. Solid symbols: artificial indentation induced scallops. Open symbols: dicing induced scallops. Gray bar: maximum, intrinsic strength. Dashed lines: strength bounds predicted from separate tests.

In practical terms, the lower bound calibration strength σ_L measured for known values of edge distance, Eq. (6) and the lower dashed lines in Fig. 13, was given by $\sigma_L = 320h^{-1/2}$, where $[\sigma_L] = \text{MPa}$ and $[h] = \mu\text{m}$. The lower bound for scallop size as a function of edge distance, Eq. (7) and the solid lines in Fig. 11, was given by $s = 5h$. The full lower bound prediction was obtained by forming the smooth p -norm of the intrinsic strength, σ_I , and $\sigma_L(s)$:

$$\sigma^q = \sigma_I^q + \sigma_L^q, \quad (9)$$

where q is an empirical smoothing exponent and here $q = -4$ was used. The lower dashed line in Fig. 14 is the lower bound strength prediction from Eq. (9).

The upper-bound strength prediction is based on empirical Si-specific strength and scallop size responses. The upper bound of the Si strength variation with edge distance for the indentation flaws, Fig. 13, is given by

$$\sigma \sim h^{-x}, \quad (10)$$

where x is an empirical exponent and here $x = 0.20$ was used. The variation of the Si scallop dimensions with edge distance for indentation flaws, Fig. 11(b), is given by

$$s \sim h^{0.5}. \quad (11)$$

Combining Eqs. (10) and (11) gives

$$\sigma \sim s^{-2x}. \quad (12)$$

In more detail, the proportionality terms in Eqs. (10) and (11) are decreasing and increasing functions, respectively, of indentation load. As a consequence, the proportionality term in Eq. (12) is nearly load invariant and thus explicit significant indentation load effects are not expected if strength is expressed as a function of scallop size.

In practical terms here, the upper bound calibration strength σ_U measured for known values of edge distance, Eq. (10) and the upper dashed lines in Fig. 13, was given by $\sigma_U = 270h^{-0.20}$, where $[\sigma_U] = \text{MPa}$ and $[h] = \mu\text{m}$. The upper bound for scallop size as a function of edge distance, Eq. (11) and the solid symbols in Fig. 11(b), was given by $s = 50h^{0.5}$, where $[s] = [h] = \mu\text{m}$. The full upper bound prediction was obtained by forming a p -norm as above:

$$\sigma^q = \sigma_I^q + \sigma_U^q, \quad (13)$$

where again $q = -4$. The upper dashed line in Fig. 14 is the upper bound strength prediction from Eq. (13).

The upper- and lower-bound strength predictions of Fig. 14 approach the appropriate asymptotic limits, $\sigma \sim s^{-0.4}$ and $\sigma \sim s^{-0.5}$, respectively, at large scallop dimensions. Both predictions approach the intrinsic strength limit, $\sigma_I = 529 \text{ MPa}$ at small scallop dimensions. The bounds are derived from controlled flaw indentation scallop and strength measurements. Hence it is expected that the self-consistent analysis above should describe independently measured strengths as a function of scallop size. This expectation is realized by the fact that the strength

prediction bounds enclose the control, solid symbol, indentation data of Fig. 14. The similarity in appearance of dicing-induced die fabrication scallops and indentation-induced artificial scallops, Figs. 4 and 10, leads to the expectation that the scallop-controlled strengths of both groups would be similar. This expectation is realized by the overlap of the open and closed symbol experimental data of Fig. 14 and the fact that the strength prediction bounds enclose all the strength data and match the upper bound dicing derived data.

5. Summary

Small-scale (micrometer) chips generated by light sharp contacts (Newtons) adjacent to the edges of brittle material components behave similarly to large scale chips (millimeters) formed by heavy contacts (kiloNewtons). A critical contact combination of peak load P and distance from the edge h generates a chip of characteristic size s on the free, non-contacted surface. The work here has extended to smaller scales by more than a factor of 100 the quantitative relations between P , h , and s established in a previous large-scale chip study [Chai and Lawn, 2007a] and extended the materials set to include the chipping characteristics of two industrially-relevant materials, Si and Al₂O₃-TiC. The work here has also identified and quantified the behavior of non-chip cracks prior to the onset of chipping and quantified chip size $s(P, h)$ variations for conditions beyond the critical (P, h) chipping threshold. In particular, the material-invariant chipping conditions identified earlier [Chai and Lawn, 2007a] are shown to be lower-bound chipping probability conditions.

In distinction to the focus on chip morphology in previous works [Chiu, 1998; Chai, 2011, 2017; Chai and Lawn, 2007ab] and the recent overview [Lawn, 2021], a major goal here has been prediction of the strengths of chipped components. In particular, the strengths of diced Si components generated in semiconductor microelectronics fabrication have been considered. A feature of Si dicing is the formation of chips on sawn edges in a characteristic scallop morphology. Estimation of device yield and reliability using predictions of die strength from the customary post-processing scallop quantification was thus a key motivation. Experiments and analyses here demonstrated that characterization of indentation- and dicing-induced scallop morphology, combined with limited indentation-strength tests, can be used to predict and verify dicing-controlled die strengths. In this regard, the work here should be viewed as complementary to experiments and analyses regarding strengths of dies controlled by back grinding [Cook, 2020b]. In the work here, the dies were full thickness and strengths were controlled by edge flaws arising from dicing. In the earlier work, back face ground dies were thinned prior to dicing and strengths were controlled by surface flaws arising from grinding.

Just as the earlier work on grinding flaws built on the fundamental materials science of sharp linear contacts, the scallop work here builds on the fundamental materials science of strength of sharp contacts. Specifically, as noted in the recent overview [Lawn, 2021], the chip crack generated by a sharp contact adjacent to an edge is directly analogous to the lateral crack generated by a sharp contact on a material surface far from edges. (In fact, lateral cracking is often referred to simply as “chipping” [Cook, 2015].) In the case of contacts far from edges, lateral cracks remove material and weaken indentation residual stress fields, thereby increasing the strengths associated with the two sets of half-penny cracks. This phenomenon has been well studied [Cook and Roach, 1986; Cook, 2015]. In the case of contacts adjacent to edges, one set of half-penny cracks removes material (the “scallop”) and weakens the residual field, thereby increasing the strength associated with the remaining truncated half-penny crack. The work here is a first step in quantifying this phenomenon.

From a materials engineering perspective, the dicing flaws studied here lie in the domain of one-dimensional distributions of flaws, in this case distributed along edges, and contrast with two- and three-dimensional distributions of flaws in areas (*e.g.*, grinding striations) and volumes (*e.g.*, pores), respectively. The framework to analyze the distributions of such flaws and the resulting strength distributions is well established and has been applied to sawn polycrystalline Al₂O₃ components amongst others [Cook and DelRio, 2019]. The framework has also been applied in analysis of the flaw distributions and resulting strength distributions of micro-scale microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) components. MEMS components are typically sub-millimeter in scale and formed from layers of polycrystalline Si. The strength limiting flaws in MEMS are usually nanometer-scale grain boundary grooves on component side-walls [Cook *et al.*, 2019] Such flaws thus form one dimensional distributions with a characteristic linear flaw density, just as dicing induced flaws. As the grooves are formed chemically, the flaws are smaller than the physically formed dicing edge chips. Hence MEMS strengths are much greater, a few GPa, compared with die strengths, a few hundreds of MPa. The strength framework is of course still applicable and a potential next step in edge chip analysis is to apply the strength framework to an array of edge chips.

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